

Effect of the Type of Cystic Ovaries on the Concentration of Some Hormones and Minerals in the Blood of Buffalo Female

Alaa Saleh Jasim Mohamed

Agriculture College, Al-Muthanna University, Iraq

Ali A. Z. Al-HajObaid

Faculty of Medicine, Jabir Ibn Hayyan Medical University, Iraq

Muhammad Baqir M. R. Fakhrilden

Faculty of Medicine, Jabir Ibn Hayyan Medical University, Iraq

Abstract

This study was conducted in the laboratory of graduate studies in the Department of Animal Production, College of Agriculture, Al-Muthanna University, and the laboratories of the of Jabir Ibn Hayyan Medical University during the period 22/9/2022 to 1/10/2023. The concentrations of hormones (insulin, prolactine, estrogen and luteinizing hormone) and the elements (Ca, P, Cu and Fe) were measured in the blood of buffalo females and compared the infected and the normal females. On the other hande the immature oocytes ware subjected to the experiment for in vitro maturation (UM) using the culture medium Dulbeccos Modified Eagles Medium (DMEM) treated with the nitric oxide with two concentrations : the low concentration was (3mM) and the high concentration was (5mM), to determine the effect of the cystic ovaries (follicular and luteal) ,the presence of cumulus oophorus and the concentration of nitric oxide in the percentage of (IVM) of buffalo oocytes .The result showed a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) between the three groups of buffalo ovaries on the concentration of the insulin hormone in the blood, the follicular cystic ovaries recorded the highest concentration of the insulin hormone(28.61 ± 0.15 U/mL) as compared with the luteal cystic ovaries (23.6 ± 0.29 U/mL) and the normal ovaries (24.41 ± 0.14 U/mL).

Keywords: *cystic ovaries type, hormones, minerals, blood, buffalo female.*

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Introduction

Inactive ovaries (IO) and ovarian (follicular or luteal) cysts (FC or LC) are two common ovarian diseases leading to infertility in dairy cattle causes disorders are associated with altered metabolites , hormones and minerals which decreased or elevated in body caused disturbance in homeostasis with no known effective biomarkers that can be used for early diagnosis of ovarian diseases (Song et al., 2021).

Explained that Cows had a more severe body condition score loss and these had greater levels of non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) and estradiol and lesser levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), progesterone and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) levels than non-folliculated cows and lower values

of calcium, phosphorus copper , iron and magnesium levels than non-folliculated cows (Bors & Bors, 2020).

The calcium plasma levels concentrations decreased at 2.10 mmol / L of calcium concentrations in early-warning indicators for ovarian diseases in dairy cows due to the combination of calcium in the estrus cycle and reproductive activity and performance in cattle (Yimer et al., 2018).

In case of Ovarian Cystic Diseases or Syndrome (FCD) or (FCS) in cattle or all females of farm animals as well as the size of the ovarian follicles increases in the follicular or luteinizing cyst, the concentration of copper and calcium in the blood plasma decreases as a result of the metabolic activity of copper and calcium in structure of reproductive hormones and enzymes which participate in the female reproductive cycle (De Lima et al., 2020).

Noticeable high significantly decreasing in calcium , copper and iron concentration (1.65 , 2.01 and 1.91) (ng / ml) respectively in several pathogenic states of disease (high and moderate) pathogenicity of Ovarian Cystic Diseases (Qin et al., 2022).

The concentration of copper and calcium in the blood plasma decreases in summer and autumn when compared to with concentrations in winter and spring as a result of the effect of environmental alteration in physiological and structural of body state and metabolic activity of females' body (D'Occhio et al., 2019).

Gareis et al. (2022) studied the Impaired insulin signaling pathways affect ovarian steroidogenesis in cows and explained the relationship between the insulin levels and the calcium, phosphorus copper, iron concentration which elevated or dropped in the Ovarian Cystic Diseases as a results of the hormonal and metabolic and physiological alterations in the body which linked with reproductive activity in females.

This study aimed the effect of the type of cystic ovaries on the concentration of some hormones and minerals in the blood of buffalo female.

Materials and Methods

Ovaries

Two hundred and eighty buffaloes ovaries were evaluated from the types of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) used. The source of buffalo eggs were ovaries obtained from the local Al-Muthanna slaughterhouse and the local Najaf slaughterhouse immediately after slaughtering the animals. The ovaries were diagnosed other, or presence of a follicular cyst, or presence of by a corpus luteum cyst.

Collection and Classification of the Buffalo Ovaries and Oocytes

Buffalo ovaries were collected from the local slaughterhouse in Muthanna and the local slaughterhouse in Najaf immediately after slaughtering the animals and placed in plastic containing a normal saline solution (0.9% sodium chloride) supplemented with antibiotics (100 IU/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin). Then it was placed in a thermos at a temperature of 30-35 ° C. The ovaries were transferred to the laboratory of the College of Agriculture and the laboratory of the College of Medicine, Jabir Bin Hayyan Medical University, within less than 1-1.5 hours. In vitro, ovaries (panel 1) were washed three times with warm normal saline (37°C) described above to remove coagulation and reduce contamination on the surface of the ovaries (Rizk, 2009).

The condition of the ovaries is diagnosed as normal or as having PCOS, which is classified according to the type of PCOS (cystic corpus luteum or cystic corpus luteum). Oocytes were collected from all follicles visible on the ovarian surface with a diameter greater than 2 mm using an aspiration technique. Oocytes with follicular fluid were aspirated using a 20-gauge hypodermic needle attached to a sterile disposable

syringe containing 0.5 mL of SMART medium supplemented with 20 IU/mL heparin to prevent coagulation of the follicular fluid. After oocyte retrieval, the content of each injection was poured into a Petri dish. This content was then examined under a dissecting microscope to collect eggs using a modified pasture pipette and washed for three times with SMART medium (DeSmedt et al., 1992).

Figure 1. Buffalo Ovaries after Washing

Classification of Oocytes

After collection, oocytes were washed three times using SMART medium, they were counted and classified under inverted microscope into immature, mature and atretic oocytes according to presence of 1st polar body and some morphological features of oocytes (Nogueira et al., 2009; Cavilla et al., 2008).

In vitro Maturation (IVM)

The oocytes were washed using SMART containing 5% HSA to remove substances in follicular fluid. The immature oocytes were directly distributed in average of 5 oocytes per droplet (0.5mL) from Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM), supplied with 10 IU/mL hCG, 5 IU/mL PMSG and 1 μ g/mL estradiol and cultured in four well dish and covered with liquid paraffin, then incubated for 24 h in CO₂ incubator (5% CO₂) at 38.5°C with 100% humidity.

Results

Table (1) shows a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) between the three groups of buffalo ovaries on the concentration of the insulin hormone in the blood, the follicular cystic ovaries were recorded a highest concentration of the insulin hormone (28.61 ± 0.15 U/ml) as correlated with the luteal cystic ovaries (23.6 ± 0.29 U/ml) and the normal ovaries (24.41 ± 0.14 U/ml), the normal ovaries were recorded the highest concentration of LH (1.003 ± 0.028 U/ml) as compared with the follicular cystic ovaries (0.596 ± 0.02 IU/ml) and the luteal cystic ovaries (0.516 ± 0.2 IU/ml). The concentration of the prolactin hormone was recorded highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) between the three groups of ovaries, whereby the luteal cystic ovaries should the highest concentration of the prolactin hormone (1.050 ± 0.03 ng/ml) as compared with the follicular cystic ovaries (0.883 ± 0.03 ng/ml) and the normal ovaries (0.600 ± 0.02 ng/ml), while the result shows a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) between the three groups of buffalo ovaries on the concentration of the estrogen hormone, whereby the follicular cystic ovaries recorded the highest concentration of the estrogen hormone (51.93 ± 0.18 pg/ml) as compared with the normal ovaries (42.14 ± 0.14 pg/ml) and the luteal cystic ovaries (39.38 ± 0.18 pg/ml).

Table 1. Effect of the Type of Cystic Ovaries on the Concentration of Some Hormones in the Blood of Buffalo Females

The group	Mean \pm standard error			
	Hormone Insulin (mIU/ml)	LH Hormone (mIU/ml)	Hormone Prolactin (ng/ml)	Hormon Estrogen (pg/ml)
normal/control	0.14 \pm 24.41b	0.028 \pm 1.003a	0.02 \pm 0.600c	0.14 \pm 42.14b
luteal cyst	0.29 \pm 23.64c	0.02 \pm 0.516c	0.03 \pm 1.050a	0.18 \pm 39.38c
follicular cyst	0.15 \pm 28.61a	0.02 \pm 0.596b	0.03 \pm 0.883b	0.18 \pm 51.93a
significant	**	**	**	**

Averages with different letters within one column differ significantly from each other. **($P \leq 0.01$).

Table (2) shows a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) among the three groups of buffalo ovaries (normal, luteal and follicular cystic) on the concentration of minerals (Ca, Cu, P and Fe) in the blood of buffalo females. The animal with cystic ovaries recorded the highest concentration of Ca in the blood (24.63 ± 0.25 mg/ dl) as compared with the luteal cystic ovaries (20.07 ± 0.25 mg/dl) and the normal ovaries (17.88 ± 0.11 mg/dl), also the result shows a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) among the three groups of buffalo ovaries on the concentration of Cu element in the blood, where the follicular cystic ovaries recorded. the highest concentration of the Cu element (366.20 ± 1.02 μ g/dl) as compared with the normal ovaries (345.10 ± 0.27 μ g/dl) and the luteal cystic ovaries (332.90 ± 1.45 μ g/dl). The concentration of the P element shoude a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) among the three groups of buffalo ovaries , the highest concentration of P element in the blood was recorded in the group of follicular cystic ovaries (3.83 ± 0.06 mg/ dl) as compared with the luteal cystic ovaries (3.33 ± 0.06 mg/dl) and the normal ovaries (2.79 ± 0.04 mg/dl), meanwhile the concentration of the Fe element recorded a highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) among the three groups of buffalo ovaries , the highest concentration of Fe element in the blood was recorded in the group of follicular cystic ovaries (211.67 ± 0.56 mg/ dl) as compared with the luteal cystic ovaries (208.00 ± 0.45 mg/dl) and the normal ovaries (186.23 ± 0.41 mg/dl).

Table 7. Effect of the Type of Cystic Ovaries on the Concentration of Some Minerals in the Blood of Buffalo Females

The groups	mean \pm std. error			
	Ca (Mg/dl)	Cu (Micg/dl)	P (Mg/dl)	Fe (Micg/dl)
normal/control	0.11 \pm 17.88c	0.27 \pm 345.10b	0.04 \pm 2.79c	0.41 \pm 186.23c
luteal cyst	0.25 \pm 20.07b	1.45 \pm 332.90c	0.06 \pm 3.33b	0.45 \pm 208.00b
follicular cyst	0.25 \pm 24.63a	1.02 \pm 366.20a	0.06 \pm 3.83a	0.56 \pm 211.67a
significant	**	**	**	**

Averages with different letters within one column differ significantly from each other. **($P \leq 0.01$).

Discussions

The present study was conducted to determine the effect of the polycystic ovaries syndrome (follicular and luteal) on the fertility of buffalo females represented by the percentage of in vitro maturation and the concentration of some hormones and elements in the blood of the buffalo females, also to determine the effect of presence of cumulus oophorus and the concentration of nitric oxide in the percentage of in vitro maturation of buffalo oocytes. The reproductive efficiency of buffalo is relatively poor regardless of their location throughout the world. Buffalo exhibit several well-known reproductive problems including delayed onset of puberty, poor onset of estrus, ovarian inactivity for a longer period after birth,

and most importantly, lower pregnancy rates, especially when raised in pens (Gordon, 1996). The buffalo fertility can be achieved by improving management and nutrition (Qureshi et al., 2007).

Conclusion

Buffaloes are considered slow-breeding animals, as reproductive efficiency in buffalo is inverse it is affected by some factors, such as late maturity and weak signs of estrus, especially during the season Summer, muted heat, irregular estrous cycle, seasonality in reproduction, weak pregnancy rate, and death in early embryos. Buffalo can exhibit an estrous cycle throughout the year in the tropical and hot regions Provided that adequate nutrition is provided to maintain reproductive efficiency, and it is seasonally multiple With distance from the equator due to environmental factors and photoperiod (Borghese & Moioli, 2011).

References

- Borghese, A., & Moioli, B. (2011). Buffalo: Mediterranean region. In J. W. Fuquay, P. F. Fox, & P. L. H. McSweeney (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Dairy Sciences* (2nd ed., pp. 780–784). Academic Press.
- Bors, S. I., & Bors, A. (2020). Ovarian cysts, an anovulatory condition in dairy cattle. *Journal of Veterinary Medical Science*, 82(10), 1515–1522. <https://doi.org/10.1292/jvms.20-0381>
- Cavilla, J. L., Kennedy, C. R., Byskov, A. G., & Hartshorne, G. M. (2008). Human immature oocytes grow during culture for IVF. *Human Reproduction*, 23(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dem178>
- De Lima, M. A., Morotti, F., Bayeux, B. M., de Rezende, R. G., Botigelli, R. C., De Bem, T. H. C., Fontes, P. K., Nogueira, M. F. G., Meirelles, F. V., Baruselli, P. S., da Silveira, J. C., Perecin, F., & Seneda, M. M. (2020). Ovarian follicular dynamics, progesterone concentrations, pregnancy rates and transcriptional patterns in *Bos indicus* females with a high or low antral follicle count. *Scientific Reports*, 10, 19557. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-76580-5>
- DeSmedt, V., Crozed, N., Ahmed-Ali, M., Martino, A., & Cogine, Y. (1992). In vitro maturation and fertilization of goat cells. *Theriogenology*, 37, 1049–1060.
- D'Occhio, M. J., Baruselli, P. S., & Campanile, G. (2019). Influence of nutrition, body condition, and metabolic status on reproduction in female beef cattle: A review. *Theriogenology*, 125, 277–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2018.12.008>
- Gareis, N. C., Rodríguez, F. M., Moreyra, M. L., Stassi, A. F., Angeli, E., Etchevers, L., Salvetti, N., Ortega, H., Hein, G., & Rey, F. (2022). Contribution of key elements of nutritional metabolism to the development of cystic ovarian disease in dairy cattle. *Theriogenology*, 197, 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2022.01.028>
- Nogueira, D., Ron-El, R., Friedler, S., Schachter, M., Raziel, A., Cortvrindt, R., & Smitz, J. (2009). Meiotic arrest in vitro by phosphodiesterase 3-inhibitor enhances the maturation capacity of human oocytes and allows subsequent embryonic development. *Biology of Reproduction*, 74, 177–184. <https://doi.org/10.1095/biolreprod.109.077695>
- Qin, X., Zhao, Y., Zhang, T., Yin, C., Qiao, J., Guo, W., & Lu, B. (2022). TrkB agonist antibody ameliorates fertility deficits in aged and cyclophosphamide-induced premature ovarian failure model mice. *Nature Communications*, 13, 914. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28645-8>

- Qureshi, M. S., Khan, S., & Ahmad, N. (2007). Pregnancy depresses milk yield in dairy buffaloes. *Italian Journal of Animal Science*, 6(Suppl. 2), 1290–1293.
- Rizk, B. (2009). Symposium: Update on prediction and management of OHSS. Genetics of ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome. *Reproductive Biology and Endocrinology Online*, 19(1), 14–27.
- Song, Z., Zhou, Y., Bai, X., & Zhang, D. (2021). A practical nomogram to predict early death in advanced epithelial ovarian cancer. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 11, 655826. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2021.655826>
- Yimer, N., Haron, A. W., & Yusoff, R. (2018). Determination of ovarian cysts in cattle with poor reproductive performance using ultrasound and plasma progesterone profile. *Veterinary Medicine – Open Journal*, 3(1), 1–9.

